

Milestone: MS8 - Incremental demonstrator

Lead Participant: CSC

Author: Dylan Spalding

Due: October 2024

Date Of Completion: 20/11/2024

Means of Verification

Two presentations at the General Assembly in Lisbon on November 2024, one for the Allele Frequency browser and one for the cancer and infectious disease use cases.

Video demonstrator made of the Cancer Use case.

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

Yes, delayed to be presented at the General Assembly

Project participants & others

Members of WP3 contributed to this milestone.

Participating nodes were: Finland, Norway, Portugal, Luxembourg, Sweden, Spain

Video by Anna Hagwall (UU), Kjell Peterson (UiO), Zippy Tseng (ELIXIR Hub), Elaine Harrison (ELIXIR Hub)

Next action steps

Record Allele Frequency video and report in D3.6

